

HEVC fingerprinting: conventional vs. ML methods. Case study: organic video content

Mohamed Allouche^{1,2}, Mihai Mitrea¹, Carl De Sousa Trias¹

1 SAMOVAR, Télécom SudParis, Institut Polytechnique de Paris, 91120 Palaiseau, France

2 VIDMIZER, Paris, France

Résumé : Les solutions de traçage du contenu vidéo par extraction d’empreinte numérique (*digital fingerprinting*) sont couramment utilisées pour apparier les séquences dérivées d’un même contenu par des opérations gardant l’information sémantique tout en modifiant complètement les représentations numériques. Si les méthodes de l’état de l’art visent à extraire cette empreinte directement à partir des pixels des trames vidéo, notre étude explore la possibilité d’extraire une telle signature à partir des éléments syntaxiques du flux codé MPEG-HEVC. Une chaîne de traitement est ainsi proposée et la preuve de concepts sous-jacente est amenée à travers des expériences effectuées sur un corpus vidéo de relevance métier pour les applications MarTech liées à la vidéo organique.

Mots clés : traçage vidéo, vidéo fingerprinting, codage avec pertes, MPEG-HEVC.

Abstract: Digital fingerprinting regroups theoretical and methodological tools designed for near-duplicated video content tracking back to its original representations. To this end, current day solutions exploit information extracted from the video sequence at the pixel frame level. In contrast, the present study explores the possibility of extracting digitally fingerprints directly at the level of the MPEG-HEVC stream syntax elements. The proof of concepts is obtained out of an experimental study processing an organic video corpus of business relevance for MarTech.

Key words: video tracking, fingerprinting, lossy encoding, MPEG-HEVC

1 Introduction

Video becomes the most exchanged, stored, and processed digital asset in the world: the TV over Internet traffic tripled between 2016 and 2021, reaching a monthly total of 42,000 petabytes [1], while more than 500 hours of content are uploaded to YouTube every minute [2].

In parallel, the term MarTech was coined: it covers the business and research efforts situated at the cross-roads of MARKeting and digital TECHnologies. While the video advertising is still dominated by the paid content (content created by the advertiser that pays an announcer for its distribution), organic video content is slowly but surely advancing. Organic content refers to a content whose creation and/or distribution is not paid, e.g. some user-created content with implicit advertising value, or some advertising content distributed by a user on a social network.

In practice, such a content is often shared by other users, on the same or on different social networks, thus creating a virtual chain distribution that is studied by marketing experts.

When trying to project this organic video distribution process on the multimedia processing realm, several approaches are possible. The simplest of them considers that the original video content is subsequently near duplicated¹ at each new sharing. Thus, the tracking of organic video can be ensured by video fingerprinting (also referred to as content-based copy detection or near duplicate detection) that regroups research efforts devoted to identifying duplicated and/or replicated versions of a given video sequence (query) in a reference video dataset [3, 4].

Video fingerprints are compact digital representations extracted from the video itself and are meant to uniquely identify videos even if their contents undergo a predefined, application dependent set of transformations. Two main properties apply to fingerprinting methods. First, the unicity (or uniqueness) property assumes that semantically different contents result in different fingerprints (in the sense of the similarity measure and of its related threshold). Secondly, the robustness property relates to the possibility of identifying as similar sequences that are near-duplicated. These two properties are generally evaluated according to the binary decision criteria, like the probabilities of false alarm (P_{fa}) and missed detection (P_{md}), as well as by *Accuracy*, *Precision* and *Recall*.

The present paper investigates whether video fingerprints can be effectively extracted from HEVC compressed domain video stream. To this end, it reconsiders and extends a state-of-the-art solution devoted to uncompressed domain and provides the proof of concepts (PoC) for its usage on an organic video tracking application².

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents a concise state of the art analyze, Section 3 introduces the processing workflow we consider, Section 4 delas with experimental results while Section 6 concludes the paper and identifies perspectives for future works.

2 State-of-the-art

When extracting video fingerprints, we may spoke about uncompressed domain fingerprinting and compressed domain fingerprinting. The former considers the input video is presented as a sequence of frames and that the fingerprints are extracted directly from pixels or from some directly derives representations (ranging from DCT or DWT to SIFT or SURF). The latter are expected to extract the fingerprints from the encoded stream syntax elements.

2.1. Uncompressed domain fingerprinting

Uncompressed domain methods inherit their basic concepts from image processing, machine learning, and information theory and leverage the fingerprinting extraction on three incremental levels [6]. Frame aspect distortion invariance is obtained by extracting the fingerprinting from derived representations such as transform [5, 6], pixel differences between consecutive frames,

¹ In this study, near-duplicated content is defined according to [7] as *identical or approximately identical videos close to the exact duplicate of each other, but different in file formats, encoding parameters, photometric variations (color, lighting changes), editing operations (caption, logo and border insertion), different lengths, and certain modifications (frames add/remove)*.

² This study was developed with academic rigor; the industrial use case, provided by VIDMIZER, helps us for identifying realistic dataset and did not bias our research approach.

temporal ordinal measure of average intensity blocks in successive frames [8], salient regions [9], quantized block motion vectors, ordinal ranking of average gray level of frame blocks, ordinal histograms of frames [10,11], color layout descriptor, ...

Frame content distortion invariance is achieved by the complementary between global geometric information (e.g., centroid of gradient orientations of keyframes [12] or invariant moments of frames edge representation) and local interest points (corner features, Hessian-Affine, SIFT, or SURF).

Video format distortion invariance is handled by specific synchronization mechanisms, pair designed with the feature selection.

Such approaches can be combined with neural network-based solutions that rely (at least partially) on various types of NN, from AlexNet [13] and ResNet [14] to CapsNet [15] and LSTM [16], sometimes requiring specifically designed architectures [17].

2.2 Towards compressed domain fingerprinting

The conventional video encoding/decoding scheme is presented in Figure 1. It consists in four basic operations: Partitioning of frame sin GoP (Group of Pictures) and of the pixels of frame in blocks, Prediction of the similarities among the blocks in a frame and among successive frames, the Transformation of the prediction errors, the Quantization of coefficients thus obtained and their Entropy Coding. The decoding process is paired designed: except for the Quantization, all other operations are one-to-one functions.

Fig. 1: Main HEVC steps in video encoding/decoding

MPEG-2 motion vectors as a partial information in fingerprinting applications were exploited in [18]. In [19], the fingerprint is represented by a combination of motion vectors and uncompressed domain information. First, key frames are selected according to their visual saliency. For any selected key frame, both global and local features are extracted as the color histograms and ORB descriptors, respectively. Finally, motion vectors directly extracted from the MPEG-2 stream serve local temporal information: specifically, motion vectors angle histograms are computed. Hence, the fingerprint is a combination of the color histograms, ORB descriptors and motion vector normalized histogram. The matching procedure is individually performed at the level of the three components (i.e., based on their individual appropriate matching criteria) and the overall

decision is achieved through fusing decisions made on multiple features by a weighted additive voting model.

2.3 Summary

This concise analysis brings to light the complementarities between uncompressed and compressed domain methods. On the one hand, uncompressed domain techniques process binary representations featuring a tremendous amount of visual redundancy, hence they are likely to achieve better applicative performances. On the other hand, compressed domain techniques are appealing by their reduced complexity in an era when the video content is practically always stored and exchanged in compressed domain. Yet, doubts about their very feasibility arise: how can fingerprinting be extracted in a domain in which the visual information is (virtually) no longer available?

Actually, while myriad of state-of-the-art solutions are available today [20], a huge disparity between these two trends can be identified: more than 30 solutions belong to the former class while only 3 to the latter class.

3 Method presentation

To reduce the fingerprinting algorithm complexity, the challenge is to extract the fingerprints from representations as close as possible to the binary compressed stream. Yet, the previous attempts consider only motion vectors that are produced by the Prediction operation (hence, available in-between Inverse Transformation and Inverse Prediction).

Consequently, our study goes further and takes the challenge to investigate the possibility of ensuring fingerprint extraction closer to the compressed stream, namely in-between Dequantization and Inverse Transformation, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Specifically, the video fingerprinting is individually extracted from each I frame composing the sequence. It is represented by the set of non-zero Luma (Y) and Chroma (both C_r and C_b) coefficients.

For fingerprinting detection, two alternative solutions are to be considered:

- *Conventional detection solution*: according to conventional binary decision problem, the optimal decision rule (assuming near-duplicated modifications act as an additive Gaussian noise as well as semantically different sequences have independent fingerprints) is based on correlation. Hence, we consider a Spearman's coefficient computed between the query and the reference: it is individually applied on the three fingerprinting components Y , C_r and C_b . A decision of match is made when the correlation between the Y components and at least one of the two C_r and C_b components are above a threshold Th (whose value will be experimentally investigated in Section 4).
- *A binary decision tree method*: belonging to the machine learning methods, decision tree is a supervised learning method that creates simple decision rules to classify data. For our purpose, the decision tree is trained on 80% of the dataset (original and near duplicated modifications) and aims to distinguish one fingerprint from all the others. The input format corresponds to the length, the mean, the standard deviation, the minimal

value, and the maximal value of the component Y . Since one decision tree corresponds to one fingerprint, a decision of match is made when a decision tree identifies the query...

Fig. 2: Method positioning in the decompression pipe-line

4 Experimental results

The corpus consists of 865 original video sequences of organic video, provided by VIDMIZER. Each sequence length varies between 6 sec and 65 sec. When the original sequence has a larger length, it was cut in several chunks so as to stick to this interval. For each original video sequence, 8 near-duplicated sequences are created by applying the following types of video transformations: picture-in-picture, blurring by three different parameters, brightness changing by three different parameters, and text inserting. Each of these 8 transformations is systematically applied with in conjunction with noise addition and reencoding.

A HEVC parser based on HEVC reference software has been developed. The goal of the parser is to generate a low-level video representation without fully decoding it (hence, without extracting the pixel values). Among the seven decoding steps, only the Bitstream Parsing, Entropy decoding, Dequantization are required in our method. The parsed syntax elements are collected and grouped by type per frame. At this level, the syntax elements from all the video frames are collected and stored. The output of the parser is recorded in a collection of YAML files to facilitate future use on the extracted syntax elements. The parser is capable to separate each GOP and present the relationship between the frames forming it.

4.1 Experiment 1: Conventional fingerprinting

The fingerprinting detection is stated as a binary decision problem. The query extracted from any attacked sequence is successively compared to each and every fingerprint extracted from the original. The quantitative results are obtained by computing the mean performance on the entire dataset and are illustrated in Figures 3 and 4. Figure 3 provides P_{fa} and P_{md} as functions of the correlation threshold. Note that these two entities are proper to the fingerprinting system and,

assuming they are estimated with precision, they provide information about system regardless, of its specific conditions of its usage. When considering now the fingerprinting system in the functional framework set by the organic video tracking, its *Accuracy*, *Precision* and *Recall* are computed and illustrated in Figure 4.

When analyzing the numerical values reported in Fig. 3 it can be noticed that the P_{md} values are too high: that shows that conventional methods fail in matching the fingerprints extracted in compressed domain. This conclusion is strengthened by the values reported in Figure 4.

Fig. 3: Conventional method performances, expressed in terms of probabilities of false alarm and missed detection

Fig. 4: Conventional method performances, expressed in terms of Accuracy, Precision and Recall

4.2 Experiment 2: ML based method fingerprinting

The decision tree is based on the scikit-library with the ‘gini’ criterion, a maximal depth of 5, the minimal number of sample to create a node equal to 2, and weights on the two classes to balance the decisions.

The fingerprinting detection is stated as a binary decision problem. The query extracted and formatted from any sequence is successively process by each and every decision tree.

The quantitative results are obtained by computing the mean performance of all decision trees on the entire dataset (original and attacked sequences).

The experiments resulted in $P_{fa} = 0.098$ and $P_{md} = 0.023$.

These values can be considered as a successful PoC for the solution, thus demonstrating video fingerprinting can be achieved in compressed domain.

Although the tests are carried out in a highly unbalanced context (we only have 8 elements in the “near-duplicated” class and around 7500 in the complementary class), we also computed the overall functioning properties of the system. We thus obtained $Accuracy = 0.977$, $Prec = 0.111$ and $Rec = 0.902$. This show that system successfully recover all the replica. It is also thus showed that a significant number of false positives is obtained. Such a behavior is complementary

with respect to the conventional solution that featured a very large P_{md} value and opens the door to a possible cascading of the two approaches. When going deeper into a qualitative evaluation of these false positive, it was pointed out that they are mainly brought by content belonging to the same initial sequence (before it being chunked in less than 1min) or by content semantically close (yet different) from the query, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Fig. 5: Example of false positives induced by the ML based method. The query sequence (illustrated by the left frame) results in false positive belonging to the same content but at different time moments (illustrated by the middle frame) or by visually related contents moments (illustrated by the right frame)

5 Conclusion

The paper establishes the proof of concepts for HEVC compressed domain fingerprinting of organic video sequences. The fingerprint itself is represented by the non-zero Luma and Chroma quantized coefficients of the I frames. While the conventional (correlation-based) methods cannot solve the task, ML-based method (a basic binary decision tree) was able to identify the content with $P_{fa} = 0.098$ and $P_{md} = 0.023$. These values characterize the inner behavior of the system. Future work is devoted to identifying the applicative perimeter of the method, to a possible cascading of conventional and binary tree solutions and to the study of neural network based solutions for fingerprinting extraction.

References

- [1] Statista (2022). Statista. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/267222/global-data-volume-of-internet-video-to-tv-traffic/>.
- [2] Youtube (2023). Available at: <https://blog.youtube/press/>.
- [3] Douze, M., Gaidon, A., Jegou, H., Marszałek, M., and Schmid, C. (2008). INRIA-LEAR's video copy detection system. TRECVID.
- [4] Lee, S., and Yoo, C. D. (2008). Robust video fingerprinting for content-based video identification. IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol. 18 (7), 983–988.
- [5] Garboan, A., and Mitrea, M. (2016). Live camera recording robust video fingerprinting. Multimed. Syst. 22, 229–243.
- [6] Coskun, B., Sankur, B., and Memon, N. (2006). Spatio-temporal transform based video hashing. IEEE Trans. Multimed. 8 (6), 1190–1208.
- [7] Wu, X., Zhao, W., and Ngo, C. W. (2007). Near-duplicate keyframe retrieval with visual keywords and semantic context. Proc. of the 6th ACM international conference on image and video retrieval (CIVR'07), 162–169.
- [8] Hampapur, A., and Bolle, R. M. (2001). Comparison of distance measures for video copy detection. International conference on multimedia and expo, 737–740.

- [9] Su, X., Huang, T., and Gao, W. (2009). Robust video fingerprinting based on visual attention regions. *IEEE Int'l Conf. Acoust. Speech Signal Process* 109 (1), 1525–1528.
- [10] Kim, C., and Vasudev, B. (2005). Spatiotemporal sequence matching for efficient video copy detection. *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* 15, 127–132.
- [11] Sarkar, A., Ghosh, P., Moxley, E., and Manjunath, B. S. (2008). Video fingerprinting: features for duplicate and similar video detection and query-based video retrieval. *Multimed content access algorithms syst II*, 68200E.
- [12] Lee, S., and Yoo, C. D. (2008). Robust video fingerprinting for content-based video identification. *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* 18 (7), 983–988.
- [13] Krizhevsky, A., Sutskever, I., and Hinton, G. E. (2012). ImageNet classification with deep convolutional neural networks. *Advances in neural information processing systems 25: 26th annual conference on neural information processing systems*, 1106–1114.
- [14] He, K., Zhang, X., Ren, S., and Sun, J. (2016). Deep residual learning for image recognition. in *IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (CVPR)*, 770–778.
- [15] Sabour, S., Frosst, N., and Hinton, G. E. (2017). Dynamic routing between capsules. *Adv. neural Inf. Process. Syst.* 30.
- [16] Hochreiter, S., and Schmidhuber, J. (1997). Long short-term memory. in *Neural Comput*, 1735–1780.
- [17] Zhixiang, C., Lu, J., Feng, J., and Zhou, J. (2018). Nonlinear structural hashing for scalable video search. *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* 28, 1421–1433.
- [18] Ngo, C. W., Yu-Fei, M., and Hong, J. Z. (2005). Video summarization and scene detection by graph modeling. *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* 15, 296–305.
- [19] Ren, D., Zhuo, L., Long, H., Qu, P., and Zhang, J. (2016). MPEG-2 video copy detection method based on sparse representation of spatial and temporal features. *IEEE second international conference on multimedia big data*.
- [20] Allouche, M. and Mitrea, M. (2022) Video fingerprinting: Past, present, and future. *Front. Sig. Proc.* 2:984169.